

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET - ADULT

Version 1.0 Date 18 January 2021

Study Title: *Streptococcus pyogenes* carriage acquisition, persistence and transmission dynamics within households in The Gambia: a longitudinal cohort study - SpyCATS

SCC/Protocol No: 24005

Sponsor: MRC Unit The Gambia at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine**Funder:** The Wellcome Trust**What is informed consent?**

You are invited to take part in a research study. Participating in a research study is not the same as getting regular medical care. The purpose of a research study is to gather information that may be useful in the future for the whole population. The purpose of this research study is to understand how a germ called Strep A is transmitted amongst adults and children living in the same household. It is your decision to take part and you can stop at any time without giving any reason.

Before you decide you need to understand why the study is being done and what will happen in it. Please take time to read the following information or get the information explained to you in your language. Listen carefully and feel free to ask if there is anything that you do not understand. As the study will involve you but also your household and family, it is very important that you also discuss it amongst family members so that everyone is OK to take part too. If you decide to join the study, you and every adult in the household who is happy to contribute need to sign or thumbprint a consent form saying you understand and agree to be in the study. We will also ask your children if they are happy to take part if they are between 12 and 18 and get their agreement (assent), and you can give consent for your children in the household who are younger than 12. You will receive a copy of the form.

Why is this study being done?

Group A streptococcus, or "Strep A" is a germ that is very common all over the world, as well as in The Gambia. It usually causes infections of the throat and skin but can cause more serious illness and death. It can also lead to a type of heart disease, which is common in The Gambia.

Strep A can also live on people's skin and in their throats without making them sick, and we believe that this is how the germ passes between people. In this study we are trying to find out how common it is to carry Strep A on the skin or in the throat without being sick, how it spreads around households, and whether carrying Strep A is more likely to make you or your family sick in the future. If we can find these things out, we can design better ways to treat and prevent Strep A infections in The Gambia. We will tell the results of this study to your community.

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What does this study involve?

The study will include 60 households from Sukuta, and if you agree to take part in the study, we will visit you regularly at your home for a year. We will also ask all of the other people who live in your household to be in the study. We will normally visit the household every month, but in some cases more or less frequently depending if you are selected for an additional part of the study.

At each visit, we will ask you some questions about yourself, your health, and your usual daily activities. We will take your vital signs, and examine you, including your skin and throat. And we will take a swab from your throat, normal skin and any skin infections that we find, take a sample of your saliva, and some spots of dried blood. At some visits we will also ask to take a blood sample or ask you to come to an appointment at Sukuta Health Centre to give a blood sample.

Each time we visit your household, we will also ask you or another member of your household some questions about the household such as sleeping arrangements and water access. We will also take some samples from the compound including swabs and leaving a dish indoors for 1 hour to collect germs from the air.

If we find out that you are sick for any reason, you will receive the care routinely available in The Gambia. You may be provided with treatment at your compound, be asked to attend an MRC clinic or be referred to a health facility that can manage the condition better.

If the research study needs to be stopped for any reason, we will tell you and you will have normal medical care if you need it.

What will happen to the samples taken in this study?

The samples that we take at each visit will be taken to the MRC laboratories in Fajara. The swabs taken from your throat and skin, and the samples from the compound will be used to look for different germs including Strep A. The saliva sample, dried blood spots and blood samples will be used to test how the body's immune system reacts to Strep A. The samples may be sent to international laboratories.

With your permission, we will store all materials left over for any new research questions about Strep A that might come up in the future, and we ask you to tick the box on the consent form to say you are happy with having your samples stored for future use, which may include genetic testing. Any new research would have to be approved by the Gambia Government/MRC Joint Ethics Committee. If you do not wish to consent for future use of your samples, we can still have you participate but we would not store your samples.

What harm or discomfort can you expect in the study?

You may find that taking the swabs is uncomfortable, but it will be quick. The mouth swab for saliva does not hurt at all. The dried blood spots and blood samples can cause mild discomfort and might leave a small bruise, but the methods we are using are very safe, and the field team are well trained to take the samples as quickly and painlessly as possible.

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What benefits can you expect in the study?

The benefit to you and your household members is that you will have regular visits from our nursing team who will examine you and identify any Strep A infections, or other medical problems earlier than normal. The study team will also provide treatment for any possible Strep A infections, and some other common medical problems to you for free at the household visits.

You would also have access to our doctors and nurses in case you have another medical problem, and we can advise you and your family what to do. If we think you need to go into hospital, we will refer you to the governmental health facilities for routine care for such conditions. In some cases, we might take you to MRC hospital in Fajara.

Will you be compensated for participating in the study?

You will not get paid by the study for participation, but if you have to attend the clinic for a study-related reason, MRC will provide transport or give you back the money for your transport.

What happens if you refuse to participate in the study or change your mind later?

You are free to join the study or not and you are free to stop being in the study any time without giving a reason. You will still get the normal medical care. If you do not want to continue in the study, we will use only the samples and information already collected from you. If any new information becomes available during the study that may affect your participation, you will be informed as soon as possible.

How will personal records remain confidential and who will have access to it?

All information that is collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Your personal information will only be available to the study team members and might be seen by some rightful persons from the Ethics Committee, Government authorities and sponsor. This could include organisations outside The Gambia. Anybody outside the study team who might see such information would only do so to ensure the study was being conducted properly.

Who should you contact if you have questions?

If you have any questions or are worried you can call [REDACTED] and you can always call the personal numbers of the MRC workers given to you. Please feel free to ask any question you might have about the study.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been checked by scientists at the Medical Research Council and by the Gambia Government/MRC Joint Ethics Committee. The Ethics Committee protects your rights and wellbeing and has given permission for it to take place.

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CONSENT FORM

Household Identification Number: |__|__|__| Individual Identification Number: |__|__|__|

(Printed name of participant)

I have read the written information **OR**

I have had the information explained to me by study personnel in a language that I understand, and I:

- confirm that my choice to participate is entirely voluntarily,
- confirm that I have had the opportunity to ask questions about this study and I am happy with the answers that have been provided,
- understand that I allow access to the information about me by the persons described in the information sheet,
- had enough time to think about whether I want to take part in this study,
- agree to take part in this study.

Cross (X) as appropriate

I agree for my samples to be shipped outside of The Gambia Yes No

I agree to storage and future research on my samples/our household samples including genetic testing Yes No

Participant's signature/
thumbprint*

_____ Date Time

Printed name of witness*

Printed name of person
obtaining consent

I attest that I have explained the study information accurately in _____ and was understood to the best of my knowledge by the participant. The participant has freely given consent to participate *in the presence of the above-named witness (where applicable).

Signature of person
obtaining consent

_____ Date (dd/mmm/yyyy) Time (24hr)

* Only required if the participant is unable to read or write.

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